

Identifying and Improving Dataset References in Social Sciences Full Texts

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Abstract. Scientific full text papers are usually stored in separate places than their underlying research datasets. Authors typically make references to datasets by mentioning them for example by using their titles and the year of publication. However, in most cases explicit links that would provide readers with direct access to referenced datasets are missing. Manually detecting references to datasets in papers is time consuming and requires an expert in the domain of the paper. In order to make explicit all links to datasets in papers that have been published already, we suggest and evaluate a semi-automatic approach for finding references to datasets in social sciences papers. Our approach doesn't need a corpus of papers (no cold start problem) and it performs well on a small test corpus (gold standard). Our approach achieved an F-measure of 0.854 for identifying references in full texts and an F-measure of 0.679 for finding correct matches of detected references in the da|ra dataset registry.

Keywords. Information extraction, Link discovery, Data linking, Research data, Social sciences, Scientific papers

1. Introduction

Digital libraries have been growing enormously in recent years. They provide resources with high metadata quality, easy subject access, and support for retrieving information [1]. We are specifically interested in scientific full text papers in digital libraries. Today more and more papers in the quantitative social sciences make references to datasets. However, in most cases the papers do not provide explicit links that would provide readers with direct access to referenced datasets.

Explicit links from scientific publications to the underlying datasets and vice versa can be useful in multiple use cases. For example, if a reviewer wants to check the evaluation mentioned in a paper which is performed on a dataset, a link would give him straightforward access to the data, enabling them to check the evaluation. Or, if other

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researchers want to perform further analysis on a dataset that used in a paper, they would be able to do so.

Today, the majority of papers do not have such direct links to datasets. While there exist registries that make datasets citable, e.g., by assigning a digital object identifier (DOI) to them, they are usually not integrated with authoring tools. Therefore, in practice, authors typically cite datasets by *mentioning* them, e.g., using combinations of title, abbreviation and year of publication for citing a dataset. It is useful to make all links to datasets explicit in papers that have been published already. Manually detecting references to datasets in papers is time consuming and requires an expert in the domain of the paper. Detecting dataset references automatically is challenging since in most cases, approaches need a huge corpus of papers or training set. We therefore suggest a semi-automatic approach. The system parses full texts very fast and tries to find exact matches without possessing any training set.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- a quantitative analysis of typical naming patterns used in the titles of social sciences datasets,
- a semi-automatic approach for finding references to datasets in social sciences papers with two alternative interactive disambiguation workflows, and
- an evaluation of the implementation of our approach on a corpus of mda journal articles.

Section 2 states the problem we are facing. Section 3 introduces preliminaries of techniques and metrics which are applied in the paper. Section 4 describes the previous related literature to this problem. All used data by the suggested approach is explained in section 5. Section 6 introduces the proposed solution. The evaluation is outlined in section 7. Section 8 concludes with an outlook to future work.

2. Problem statement

Whereas a lot of effort has been spent on information extraction in general [2], fewer attempts have focused on the specific task of dataset extraction [3]. To refer to the same dataset, different papers often use different names or keywords [3]. Therefore, simple keyword or name extraction approaches do not solve the problem. References to datasets can appear in different places in a paper, as illustrated in figure 1. Each of detected references to datasets in a paper should be turned into an explicit link, for example by using the DOI of the dataset in a dataset registry. In our case, these references should be linked to items in the da|ra dataset registry.

3. Preliminaries: similarity, ranking and evaluation metrics

Our work and other researchers' related work employs certain standard metrics for ranking results of a search query (here: a text in a paper that refers to a dataset) over a corpus of documents (here: titles of datasets), and for evaluating the accuracy of information retrieval algorithms. The following three subsections introduce the definitions of these concepts.

Figure 1. The distribution of dataset references in 15 random mda papers

3.1. Weighting terms in documents using *tf-idf*

Term frequency (tf) measures the number of occurrences of a given term in a given document or query text [4]. *Inverse document frequency (idf)* is defined as $\log(N/n)$, where N is the number of all documents in a corpus and n is the number of all documents that contain the given term [4]. *tf-idf* is defined as the product of *tf* and *idf*. When ranking documents that contain a term being searched, *tf-idf* returns high scores for documents for which the given term is *characteristic*, i.e. documents that have many occurrences of the term, while the term has a low occurrence rate in *all* documents of the corpus [4]. In other words, the *tf-idf* algorithm assigns a weight to each word in a document, giving high weights to keywords and low weights to frequent words such as stop words.

3.2. The cosine similarity metric

A document can be considered as a vector in a vector space, each dimension of which corresponds to one term in the document corpus. Such a document vector looks like $d = (t_1w_1, \dots, t_nw_n)$, where $t_i = 1$ means that the term t_i exists in the document, and $t_i = 0$ means the term is absent in the document. *tf-idf* is one way of computing the weight w_i of terms. Search results for a multi-word query in a corpus of documents can be ranked by the *similarity* of each document with the query. Given a query vector q and a document vector d , their *cosine similarity* is defined as the cosine of the angle θ between the two vectors [4,5], i.e. $\text{sim}(q, d) = \cos \theta = \frac{q \cdot d}{\|q\| \|d\|}$. Combining *tf-idf* and cosine similarity yields a ranked list of documents. In practice, it may furthermore be necessary to define a cut-off threshold to distinguish documents that are considered to match the query from those that do not [6].

3.3. Precision and recall of a classifier

We aim at implementing a binary classifier that tells us whether or not a certain dataset has been referenced by a paper. The algorithm tries to find references of datasets in a

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paper and then to distinguish a perfect match for each reference in da|ra. The reliability of binary classifiers can be determined by the evaluation metrics of *precision and recall*, and furthermore by F-measure, which combines both.

4. Related work

While only a few scientific works have been found about the specific task of extracting dataset references from scientific publications, a lot of research has been done on its general foundations including metadata extraction and string similarity algorithms. Solutions for extracting keywords from papers are particularly useful for us, as references to datasets can be considered a special case of keywords. Related work can be divided into three main groups covered by the following subsections.

4.1. Methods based on the “bag of words” model

A text can be considered as a set of words and represented as a vector, which indicates absence or presence of a word in the text. In other words, we can assume a vector space, each of whose dimensions corresponds to one word. Weights for terms in such vectors need to be adjusted by weighting algorithms such as tf-idf. Lee et al. proposed an unsupervised keyword extraction method by using a tf-idf model with some heuristics [7]. Our approach uses similarity measures for finding a perfect match for each dataset reference in a paper by comparing titles of datasets in a repository to sentences in papers. Similarity measures such as Matching, Dice 2, Jaccard, Overlap and Cosine can be applied to a vector representation of a text easily (cf. [5]). The accuracy of algorithms based on such similarity measures can be improved by making them semantics-aware, e.g., representing a set of synonyms as a single vector space dimension.

4.2. Corpus and Web based methods

These methods use information about co-occurrence of two texts in documents and are used for measuring semantic similarity of texts. Singhal et al. proposed an approach to extract dataset names from articles [8]. They employed the NGD algorithm, which estimates the probability of two terms existing separately in a document as well as of their co-occurrence. They used two research engines, Google Scholar and Microsoft Academic Search, instead of a local corpus. Schaefer et al. proposed the Normalized Relevance Distance (NRD) [9]. This metric measures the semantic relatedness of terms. NRD is based on co-occurrence of terms in documents and extends NGD by using relevance weights of terms. The quality of these methods depends on the size of used corpus.

4.3. Machine learning methods

Many different machine learning approaches have been employed for extracting metadata, in a few cases also for detecting dataset references. For example, Zhang et al. proposed keyword extraction methods based on support vector machines (SVM) [10].

Kaur et al. conducted a survey on several effective keyword extraction techniques, such as conditional random field (CRF) algorithms [11]. CRF classifiers can assign labels

to sequences of input and for instance, define which parts in a paper can be assumed to be keywords [12].

Cui et al. proposed an approach using Hidden Markov Model (HMM) to extract meta data from texts [13]. Marinai described a method for extracting metadata from documents by using a neural classifier [14]. Lu et al. used the feature based “Llama” classifier for detecting dataset references in documents [3]. Since there are many different styles for datasets references, large training sets are necessary for these approaches.

Boland et al. proposed a pattern induction method for extracting dataset references from documents to overcome the necessity of such a large training set [15]. Their algorithm starts with the name of a dataset, or with an abbreviation of this name, and iteratively derives patterns of phrases that contain datasets references iteratively by using a bootstrapping approach. It still requires a corpus of papers for induction of patterns.

5. Data sources

This section describes the two types of data sources that we use. We use full text articles from the journal *mda* to evaluate the performance of our dataset linking approach, and metadata of datasets in the *da|ra* dataset registry to identify datasets.

5.1. Papers from *mda* journal

Methods, data, analyses (*mda*⁵) is an open-access journal which publishes research on all questions important to quantitative methods, with a special emphasis on survey methodology. It published research on all aspects of science of surveys, be it on data collection, measurement, or data analysis and statistics. All content of *mda* is freely available and can be distributed without any restrictions, ensuring the free flow of information that is crucial for scientific progress. We use a random sample of full text articles from *mda*.

5.2. The *da|ra* dataset registry

5.2.1. *da|ra* overview

The dataset reference extraction approach presented works for social sciences datasets registered in the *da|ra* dataset registry⁶. *da|ra* offers the DOI registration service in Germany for social science and economic data.

Research data in the social sciences has been collected and made available by different institutions. Being able to access such datasets and to reuse them for further analyses is important, but information on where to find and how to access them is often missing. *da|ra* makes social science research data referenceable and thus improves its accessibility. This is achieved by assigning to each dataset a digital object identifier (DOI), a unique string that identifies an item (here: a dataset) and serves as a link to its location on the Web. *da|ra* thus does a job similar to that of publishers assigning DOIs to articles when they are published electronically.

At the time of this writing, *da|ra* holds 428,056 records (datasets, texts, collections, videos or interactive resources); 32,858 of them are datasets.

⁵<http://www.gesis.org/en/publications/journals/mda/>

⁶<http://www.da-ra.de>

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For each dataset, da|ra provides metadata including title, author, language, and publisher. This metadata is exposed to harvesters using a freely accessible API using OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting).⁷

5.2.2. Analysis of dataset titles in da|ra

We analyzed the titles of all datasets in da|ra and the titles were harvested by using the API of da|ra. The analysis shows that about one third of the titles follow a special pattern, which makes them easier to detect in the text of a paper. We have identified three such special patterns. First, there are titles that contain *abbreviations*, by which the dataset is often referred to. Consider, for example, the full title “Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), Cyprus”, which contains the abbreviation “PIAAC”. Secondly, there are *filenames*, as in the example “Southern Education and Racial Discrimination, 1880-1910: Virginia: VIRGPT2.DAT”, where “VIRGPT2.DAT” is the name of the dataset file. Finally, there are *phrases* that explicitly denote the existence of datasets in a text, such as “Exit Poll” or “Probation Survey”. “Czech Exit Poll 1996” is an example of such a dataset title. Abbreviations and special phrases can be found in about 17 and 19 percentage of the da|ra dataset titles. The intersection of these two groups is only 1.49 percent. Filenames occur in less than one percent of the titles.

6. A semi-automatic approach for finding dataset references

We have realized a semi-automatic approach to find references in a given full text to datasets registered in da|ra. The first and last steps of our algorithm require human interaction to improve the accuracy of the result.

6.1. Step 1: Preparing the dictionary

We first prepare a *dictionary* of abbreviations and of special phrases. *Abbreviations* are initially obtained by applying rules to the harvested dataset titles from da|ra. One of these rules assumes that words in capital letters between parentheses in dataset titles are abbreviations. It detects, for example, “DAWN” in “Drug Abuse Warning Network (DAWN), 2008” correctly. However, it sometimes detects words that are not references to datasets, such as “NYPD” in “New York Police Department (NYPD) Stop, Question, and Frisk Database, 2006”. Such false positives should be removed from the dictionary. As their identification is hard to automate, we left this task to a human expert.

The dictionary of *special phrases* also has to be prepared manually. A list of terms that refer to datasets such as “Study” or “Survey” has been generated manually; then, phrases containing these terms were derived by rules from titles of actual datasets in da|ra. “Media Study” and “Consumer Survey” are two examples of such phrases. The phrase list has finally been verified by a human expert.

Both dictionaries – abbreviations and phrases – have been generated on the first harvest of dataset titles from da|ra. They will require an update with every subsequent harvest.

⁷<http://da-ra.de/oaip/>

6.2. Step 2: Detecting dataset references and ranking matching datasets

Next, we *detect characteristic features* (abbreviations or phrases) of dataset titles in the full text of a given paper. A paper is split into sentences, and each of these features is searched for in each sentence. A sentence is split into smaller pieces if one feature repeats inside the sentence more than once, since such a sentence may contain references to different versions of a dataset. Any phrase identified in this step might correspond to more than one dataset title. For example, “ALLBUS”⁸ is an abbreviation for a famous social science dataset, of which more than 150 versions are registered in da|ra. These versions have different titles and for instance, the titles differ from year of study such as “German General Social Survey - ALLBUS 1998”, “German General Social Survey - ALLBUS 2010” and “German General Social Survey (ALLBUS) - Cumulation 1980-2012”. “PIAAC” is an abbreviation of another study. Two titles that contain this abbreviation are “Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), Cyprus” and “Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), Germany”, i.e., these two datasets differ by geographic coverage. We solve the problem of identifying the most likely datasets referenced by the text in the paper by *ranking* their titles with a combination of tf-idf and cosine similarity. In this ranking algorithm, we apply the definitions of section 3, where the query is a candidate dataset reference found in the paper and the documents are the titles of all datasets in da|ra.

6.3. Heuristics to improve ranking in Step 2

The approach as presented so far computes, for each reference detected in the full text of a paper, tf-idf over the full text of the paper and over the list of the titles of datasets in da|ra that contain a specific characteristic feature (abbreviation or phrase) detected in the reference. While a corpus of papers is typically huge, the size of all da|ra dataset titles and the size of the full text of an average paper are less than 4 MB each. Given this limited corpus size, our algorithm may detect some false keywords in a query, thus adversely affecting the result. For instruction, figure 2 illustrates a toy example of this problem. In

Figure 2. A toy example of cosine similarity, where tf-idf is computed over phrases in two papers and selected titles from da|ra

⁸Allgemeine Bevölkerungsumfrage der Sozialwissenschaften = German General Social Survey

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paper 1, “2014” repeats many times, whereas “study” occurs once, so tf-idf assigns a high weight to “study” and a low weight to “2014”. When the query string is “study allbus 2014”, cosine similarity give a higher rank to “Study Allbus 2000” than “Allbus 2014”. To address this problem in a better way, our implementation employs some heuristics, including an algorithm that improves the ranking of datasets based on matching years in the candidate strings in the paper and in the dataset titles. In the example, these heuristics improve the ranking of the “Allbus 2014” dataset when analyzing paper 1.

6.4. Step 3: Exposing the results to the user, and interactive disambiguation

Our application supports two workflows by which an expert user can choose the best matches for the datasets cited by a paper from a set of candidates identified automatically. The sizes of these sets have been chosen according to the observations we made during the evaluation of the automated step, as explained in section 7. One workflow works per reference: for each reference, five titles of candidate datasets are suggested to the user. While this workflow supports the user best in getting every reference right, it can be tiring: each paper in our corpus contains 45 dataset *references* on average, but these only refer to an average number of 3 distinct *datasets*. The second, alternative workflow takes advantage of this observation: it works per characteristic feature and suggests, for each feature (which may be common to multiple individual references in the paper) six titles of candidate datasets to the user. To enable even further analysis of the links identified between papers and datasets, we export for each paper an RDF graph containing all candidate datasets identified in the latter workflow. For each candidate dataset, we represent in RDF the essential metadata of the dataset: DOI, title, creator, and temporal coverage.

7. Evaluation

The calculation of evaluation metrics such as precision, recall and F-measure requires a ground truth. Regarding to this fact, we selected 15 papers randomly from the mda journal as a test corpus. These papers were selected randomly among papers which have been published in 2013 and 2014. We aimed at equal coverage of languages, picking 8 English and 7 German papers. A trained assessor reviewed all papers one by one and identified all references to datasets. Afterward, the person attempted to discover a correct match in da|ra for each detected reference so a list of existing datasets in each paper was generated. These lists were used as our gold standard and then we compared result of our algorithm for each paper with this gold standard. We decided to divide our evaluation into two parts. The first evaluation is about identifying of dataset references in papers by our approach. Accuracy of this part depends on the quality of the generated dictionaries of abbreviations and special phrases. These characteristic features are searched by our algorithm in the full texts and the detection of any of these features means a detection of a reference to a dataset. The second evaluation is for matching detected references in papers with items in the da|ra registry. Our observations in this second evaluation justify the choices of set size in the interactive disambiguation workflows. In the per-reference matching workflow, a ranked list of titles of datasets is generated for each of the, on average in our corpus, 45 dataset references in a paper by employing a combination of cosine similarity and tf-idf. Our observation shows that the correct match among da|ra

dataset titles for each reference detected is in the top 5 items of the ranked list generated by combining cosine similarity and tf-idf for that reference. Therefore, we adjusted our implementation to only keep the top 5 items of each candidate list for further analysis – such as an expert user’s interactive selection of *the* right dataset for a reference. The per-feature matching workflow categorizes references by characteristic feature. For example, in a paper that contains exactly the three detected characteristic features “AIBUS”, “PIAAC” and “exit poll”, each dataset reference relates to one of these three features. If we obtain for each such reference the list of top 5 matches as in the per-reference workflow and group these lists per category, we can count the number of occurrences of each dataset title per category. Now, looking at the dataset titles per category sorted by ascending number of occurrences, we observed that the correct matches for the datasets references using a specific characteristic feature were always among the top 6 items. The results of our two evaluations are shown in table 1.

Phase of Evaluation	Precision	Recall	F-measure
Detection	0.936	0.785	0.854
Matching	0.744	0.625	0.679

Table 1. Results of the Evaluation

8. Conclusion and future work

We have presented an approach for identifying references to datasets in social sciences papers. It works in real time and does not require any training dataset. There are just some manual tasks in the approach such as initially cleaning the dictionary of abbreviations, or making final decisions among multiple candidates suggested for the datasets cited by the given paper. We can so far identify references to one third of the datasets in the da|ra registry: datasets whose titles contain abbreviations or special phrases. We have achieved an F-measure of 0.854 for the detection task and an F-measure of 0.679 for finding correct matches for each reference in the gold standard. Although the da|ra registry is large and it is growing fast, there are still many datasets that have not yet been registered there. This circumstance will adversely affect the task of detecting references to datasets in papers and matching them to items in da|ra. After the evaluation, our observations reveal that da|ra could cover only 64 percent of datasets in our test corpus.

Future work will focus on improving the accuracy of detecting references to the datasets supported so far, and on extending the coverage to all datasets. Accuracy can be improved by better similarity metrics, e.g., taking into account synonyms and further metadata of datasets in addition to the title. Common words can be replaced by their synonym, for example when the title of a dataset contains “survey” but it is cited as “study”. Other algorithms such as identifying the central dataset(s) on which a paper is based can improve the ranked list generated by similarity metrics. The identification of central dataset(s) is possible after pairing a share of references of datasets in a given paper with titles in da|ra, and then this identification affects the ranking of rest of the references. Coverage can be improved by taking into account further datasets, which are not registered in da|ra. One promising further source of datasets is OpenAIRE, the Open

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Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe, which so far covers more than 16,000 datasets from all domains including social science but is rapidly growing thanks to the increasing attention paid to open access publishing in the EU. The OpenAIRE metadata can be consumed via OAI-PMH, or, in an even more straightforward way, as linked data (cf. our previous work [16]).

Furthermore, we will enable further reuse scenarios by also exporting RDF from the per-reference matching workflow, using state-of-the-art annotation and provenance ontologies. For each dataset reference in the paper, we will model the precise position of that reference, and the algorithm's confidence in each possible matching dataset.

In a mid-term perspective, solutions for identifying dataset references in papers that have been published already could be made redundant by a wider adoption of standards for properly citing datasets while authoring papers, and corresponding tool support for authors.

Acknowledgements This work has been funded by the DFG project "Opening Scholarly Communication in Social Sciences" (OSCOSS) under grant agreements SU 647/19-1 and AU 340/9-1, and by the European Commission under grant agreement 643410 (OpenAIRE2020).

References

- [1] D. Hienert, F. Sawitzki, and P. Mayr, "Digital Library Research in Action – Supporting Information Retrieval in Sowiport," *D-Lib Magazine*, vol. 21, no. 3/4, 2015.
- [2] S. Soderland, "Learning information extraction rules for semi-structured and free text," *Machine Learning*, vol. 34, no. 1–3, 1999.
- [3] M. Lu, S. Bangalore, G. Cormode, M. Hadjieleftheriou, and D. Srivastava, "A dataset search engine for the research document corpus," in *ICDE*, 2012.
- [4] G. Salton and C. Buckley, "Term weighting approaches in automatic text retrieval," *Information Processing and Management*, vol. 24, no. 5, 1988.
- [5] C. D. Manning and H. Schütze, *Foundations of Statistical Natural Language Processing*. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 1999.
- [6] T. Joachims, "A probabilistic analysis of the rocchio algorithm with tfidf for text categorization," in *ICML*, 1997.
- [7] S. Lee and H. joon Kim, "News keyword extraction for topic tracking," in *Networked Computing and Advanced Information Management (NCM '08). Fourth International Conference*, vol. 2, 2008.
- [8] A. Singhal and J. Srivastava, "Data extract: Mining context from the web for dataset extraction," *International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing*, vol. 3, no. 2, 2013.
- [9] C. Schaefer, D. Hienert, and T. Gottron, "Normalized relevance distance a stable metric for computing semantic relatedness over reference corpora," in *ECAI*, 2014.
- [10] K. Zhang, H. Xu, J. Tang, and J. Li, "Keyword extraction using support vector machine," in *WAIM*, 2006.
- [11] J. Kaur and V. Gupta, "Effective approaches for extraction of keywords," *IJCSI International Journal of Computer Science*, vol. 7, no. 6, 2010.
- [12] C. Zhang, H. Wang, Y. Liu, D. Wu, Y. Liao, and B. Wang, "Automatic keyword extraction from documents using conditional random fields," *Computational and Information Systems*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2008.
- [13] B.-G. Cui and X. Chen, "An improved hidden markov model for literature metadata extraction," in *ICIC*, 2010.
- [14] S. Marinai, "Metadata extraction from pdf papers for digital library ingest-document analysis and recognition," in *ICDAR*, 2009.
- [15] K. Boland, D. Ritze, K. Eckert, and B. Mathiak, "Identifying references to datasets in publications," in *TPDL*, 2012.
- [16] S. Vahdati, F. Karim, J.-Y. Huang, and C. Lange, "Mapping large scale research metadata to linked data: A performance comparison of HBase, CSV and XML," in *MTSR*, 2015.